

The Effect Of Investment, Labour, And Inflation On The Production Value Of Agricultural Processing Industries In Southeast Sulawesi Province

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the effect of investment, labour, and inflation on the production value of agricultural processing industries in twelve regencies and cities in Southeast Sulawesi between 2011 and 2020. The study used secondary data of a data panel with the Error Correction Model analysis tool. The ECM-panel results showed that there were differences in the characteristics of the production value of the agricultural product processing industry between districts/cities. In addition, this study also revealed that investment and labour have a positive and significant effect on the production value of the agricultural product processing industry in the short and long term. Meanwhile, inflation have no significant effect on the production value of agricultural processing industries, both in the short and long term. The agricultural production value development was dominated by small and medium enterprises with relatively small and fluctuating investments, resulted in low employment. It is critical to accelerate industrial estates to create a stable investment climate and increase farmers' productivity in maintaining the sustainability of industrial raw materials.

Introduction

The economic development of Southeast Sulawesi Province is structurally dominated by the agriculture, fishery, and forestry sectors. Meanwhile, manufacturing industries had minor contributions to the GRDP (Gross Regional Domestic Product) of Southeast Sulawesi Province, as shown in Figure 1.1.

Figure 1.1. The 2016-2020 contribution of the agriculture and manufacturing industries to the GRDP of Southeast Sulawesi (Statistics Agency Indonesia, 2021)

Figure 1.1 shows that The agriculture, fishery, and forestry sectors substantially contributed to the Southeast Sulawesi Gross Regional Domestic Product in 2020, i.e., 22.32%. Meanwhile, manufacturing industries only made a minor contribution, i.e., 7.04% in 2020. This condition happened because the agriculture, fishery, and forestry sectors were sources of raw materials for agricultural processing industries. In the long term, value added industry, economic growth to value added agriculture will have a unidirectional relationship (Bashir et al., 2019). This finding supports the concept that the agricultural sector plays a vital role in economic growth and growth in other sectors, especially the industrial sector. The development of agricultural processing industries can create a diverse range of competitive agricultural products that can increase added value and create more employment. Colmer (2020) stated that the non-agricultural sector, specifically the industrial sector, could create employment and overcome agricultural productivity problems.

The abundance of raw materials from the agricultural, fishery, and forestry sectors, could not improve the role of manufacturing industries in Southeast Sulawesi. The contribution of agricultural processing industries to GRDP (Gross Regional Domestic Product) has continued to decrease annually.

The contribution of the agricultural product industries to the GRDP (GROSS REGIONAL DOMESTIC PRODUCT) of the manufacturing industries in Southeast Sulawesi is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1.2. The contribution of agricultural product industries to the GRDP of manufacturing industries in Southeast Sulawesi

Figure 1.2 shows that the contribution of agricultural product industries to the manufacturing sector in Southeast Sulawesi is dominated by the food and beverage industries; however, its contribution has consistently decreased annually. In 2016, the contribution of the food and beverage industries was 54.06% but decreased to 43.24% in 2020. A similar condition also happened to the wood and furniture industries. Sufficient natural resources are required to increase the production value of agricultural processing industries. It also needs other factors, such as investment, labour, and inflation.

Previous studies have examined the effect of investment on the production value of manufacturing industries. Djulius et al. (2019) discovered that domestic investment (DI) and foreign direct investment (FDI) affected the added value of manufacturing industries. Noorbakhsh et al. (2001) studied 36 countries rich in natural resources with favourable investment climates. The study discovered that FDI positively impacted sustainable macroeconomic growth, domestic market development, and foreign trade. Furthermore, Lestari (2021) stated that investment in the industrial sector (domestic investment) had a significant negative effect on the added value of manufacturing in the short and long term. However, Dewi (2009) stated that domestic investment had no significant effect on the industrial sector's output in the Bekasi Regency. Falki (2016) discovered that FDI had a static insignificant negative relationship with GRDP (is in Pakistan. Meanwhile, Peres et al. (2018) and Raja Aziz & Azmi (2011) found that foreign investment in developing countries was dominant, particularly encouraging long-term economic growth.

Romer et al. (2007) stated that four primary sources of economic growth are resources, capital, technology, and labour. More importantly, the potential of labour is not limited. The productivity of workers can be increased in the short or long term, through education. Furthermore, Holman, Joyeux, and Kas (2008) stated that investment and labour productivity are the main factors in improving the quality of the industrial sector. Meanwhile, Akay and Can (2012) stated that an increase in labour supply could increase output in all industries. However, Lestari (2021) discovered that labour did not significantly affect manufacturing added value in the short and long term. Inflation is another factor that may affect the production value. According to Sadono (2004), inflation is the process of price increase in an economy. Previous studies have investigated the effect of inflation on the production value of manufacturing industries. Ananda (2020) discovered that inflation did not affect the GRDP (GROSS REGIONAL DOMESTIC PRODUCT) of the industrial sector. Furthermore, Akutey et al. (2016) discovered a significant negative relationship between inflation and productivity in the manufacturing sector. Gyamfi et al. (2020) demonstrated that inflation had a significant negative effect on GRDP growth in West Africa. The study used a pooled OLS.

Table 1.2. presents the number of business units, labour, and inflation in agricultural processing industries in Southeast Sulawesi.

Table 1.1. The Labour, Investment Value, rate of Inflation, and production value of agricultural processing industries in Southeast Sulawesi between 2011-2020

Year	Number of Unit	Labour(person)	Investment IDR (000)	Inflation (%)	Production Value IDR (000)
2011	7,533	38,193	1,061,935,983	5.09	2,057,140,142
2012	7,409	37,512	1,142,557,037	5.25	2,126,062,323
2013	6,163	29,114	772,614,577	5.92	2,085,329,512
2014	6,311	29,222	752,840,584	7.4	2,005,470,083
2015	11,881	31,185	803,657,324	1.64	2,849,041,988
2016	6,317	32,444	822,213,839	0.13	2,281,472,907
2017	6,579	31,065	783,692,418	0.68	2,121,652,332
2018	1,986	19,238	595,459,427	2.55	1,291,928,363
2019	4,607	44,453	2,192,526,036	3.22	2,606,097,045
2020	3,418	17,036	991,076,320	1.33	747,643,044

Data Source: Statistics Agency Indonesia and Southeast Sulawesi industry department, 2021

The background and previous empirical studies have encouraged the authors to study the effect of investment, labour, and inflation on the production value of agricultural processing industries. The result of the study is expected to optimize the utilization of production factors in increasing the contribution of the manufacturing sector to the GRDP (Gross Regional Domestic Product) of Southeast Sulawesi.

Literature Review

The Solow model focuses on four variables, namely output (Y), capital (K), labour (L), and knowledge or work effectiveness (A). The economy always consists of three things, i.e., capital, labour, and knowledge; combined to produce output. In addition, Solow-Swan used a production function model that allows substitution between capital (K) and labour (L). (Romer, 2012)

Furthermore, Solow (1956) stated that growth depends on savings that can be used as an investment which will accelerate capital accumulation as a proposition for labour productivity and income in the model.

Previous Empirical Studies

Previous studies have examined the effect of investment, labour, and inflation on the production value. Ding et al. (2021) examined the role of foreign capital and economic freedom in sustainable food production in developing and non-developing countries. The study used a dynamic GMM panel data system and a causality test. It demonstrated that foreign capital had a positive role in food production in developing countries.

Soumia and Abderrezak (2013) analyzed the FDI determinants that impacted growth. The analysis was carried out using the panel data of AMU States between 1980-2010 with a dynamic panel system and a GMM estimator. The study demonstrates that FDI, in the long run, positively affected growth rates and improved the economic situation in Algeria, Morocco, and Tunisia. Meanwhile, Peres et al. (2018) and Raja Aziz and Azmi (2011) show that foreign investment in developing countries had a dominant role, i.e., encouraging long-term economic growth.

Merlynda (2009) investigated the effect of investment and labour on the industrial sector's output in the Bekasi Regency. The study, which was analyzed using the Ordinary Least Square (OLS) method, discovered that foreign investment and exports influenced the industrial sector's output in the Bekasi Regency. Meanwhile, domestic investment, the number of workers, and imports had no significant effect on the industrial sector's output.

RESEARCH METHOD

This study used quantitative data, i.e., secondary data published by Statistics Indonesia, the Southeast Sulawesi Industry and Trade Office, and Bank Indonesia. Based on the object and time, it used the 2011-2020 time series and cross-section data. The dependent variable in this study is the production value of agricultural processing industries in twelve regencies and cities in Southeast Sulawesi between 2011 - 2020, expressed in millions of rupiah. While the independent variables are the investment in the agricultural processing industries (INV), expressed in millions of rupiah, the labour in the agricultural processing industries (X1), expressed in the number of people, and inflation (INF), expressed in percentage, between 2011 – 2020 in twelve regencies and cities in Southeast Sulawesi.

Data Analysis

The Error Correction Model (ECM) - Panel Data approach was used to analyze the effect of investment, labour, and inflation on the production value of agricultural processing industries in Southeast Sulawesi. This model is used to verify the results of a spurious regression or overcome non-stationary data. It can also explain short and long-term parameters between time and between individuals.

Based on Widarjono (2013), the ECM model analysis procedure is described below.

1. Unit Root Test

The unit root test is used to test the stationarity of the time-series data. A non-stationary time-series data indicates that the data faces a unit root problem, which can be identified by comparing the t-statistic value of the regression with the Augmented Dickey-Fuller test value. The equation model is presented below.

$$\Delta Y_{it} = \gamma Y_{it-1} + a_2 T + Y_{it-1} + \sum_{i=1}^p \beta_1 \Delta + et \tag{4.1}$$

$$\Delta Y = \alpha_0 + \gamma Y_{it-1} + a_2 T + Y_{it-1} + \sum_{i=1}^p \beta_1 \Delta Y_{it-1} + et \tag{4.2}$$

$$\Delta Y = a_1 + a_2 T + \gamma Y_{it-1} + \sum_{i=2}^p \beta_1 \Delta Y_{it-1} + et \tag{4.3}$$

Y is the observed variable $\Delta Y_{it} = (Y_{it} - Y_{it-2})$; T is the time trend; and I is the individual cross-section. Data stationarity is determined by comparing the ADF statistic value and the critical value of the statistical distribution. The ADF statistic value is determined by the statistical value of the coefficient γY_{it-1} in equations 4.1. to 4.3. The observed data is stationary if the absolute ADF statistic value is greater than the critical value. Meanwhile, the data is non-stationary if the absolute ADF statistic value is less than the critical value. It is critical to determine the lag time during the ADF test based on the AIC or SIC criteria.

2. Order of Integration Test

The order of integration test is carried out if the unit root test shows that the observed time-series data is non-stationary. The test will reveal the order of integration required to make the data stationary. The equation model used for the test is detailed below.

$$\Delta 2Y_{it} = \gamma Y_{it-1} + \sum_{i=2}^p \beta_1 \Delta 2Y_{it-i+1} + et \tag{4.4}$$

$$\Delta 2Y_{it} = \alpha_0 + \gamma Y_{it-1} + \sum_{i=2}^p \beta_1 \Delta 2Y_{it-i+1} + et \tag{4.5}$$

$$\Delta 2Y_{it} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 T + \gamma Y_{it-1} + \sum_{i=2}^p \beta_1 \Delta 2Y_{it-i+1} + et \tag{4.6}$$

Data stationarity is determined by comparing the ADF statistic value obtained from the γ coefficient and the critical value of the Mackinnon statistical distribution. The data is considered first-order stationarity if the absolute ADF statistic value is greater than the critical value of the first-order differences. However, suppose the absolute ADF statistic value is less than the critical value. In that case, the order of the integration test needs to be continued at a higher difference to reach stationarity.

3. Cointegration Test

The most commonly used cointegration test is the Engle-Granger (EG) test, which uses a long-term regression equation.

$$Ln NP_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 LnINV_{it} + \beta_2 LnTK_{it} + \beta_3 LnINF_{it} + e_{it} \tag{4.7}$$

$Ln NP_{it}$ = The production value of agricultural processing industries (expressed in millions of IDR)

$LnINV_{it}$ = Gross fixed capital formation of the manufacturing industry sector (expressed in Million of IDR)

$LnTK_{it}$ = Number of workers in agricultural processing industries (expressed as the number of people)

$LnINF_{it}$ = inflation rate (expressed in years)

e_{it} = Disturbing variables

Equation 4.7 results in the residual (error terms), which is continued to be tested using DF or ADF. The following are the equations.

$$\Delta e_t = \beta_1 e_{t-1} \dots \tag{4.8}$$

$$\Delta e_t = \beta_1 e_{t-1} + \sum_{i=2}^p \alpha_i e_{t-i} \dots \tag{4.9}$$

The estimated statistical values of DF and ADF are then compared with their critical values. The statistical value of DF and ADF is obtained from the coefficient β_1 . The observed variables are cointegrated or have a long-term relationship if the statistical value is greater than the critical value and vice versa.

The ECM-EG equation for short-term estimates is presented below.

$$DNP_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 D\ln INV_{it} + \beta_2 D\ln TK_{it} + \beta_3 D\ln INF_{it} + \beta_4 D\ln INV_{it-1} + \beta_5 D\ln TK_{it-1} + \beta_6 D\ln INF_{it-1} + \beta_7 ECT \quad (4.10)$$

$D\ln NP_{it}$ = Change in the production value of agricultural processing industries (expressed in millions of IDR)

$D\ln IN_{it}$ = Change in the gross fixed capital formation of agricultural processing industries (expressed in millions of IDR)

$D\ln TK_{it}$ = Change in the number of workers in agricultural processing industries (expressed as the number of people)

$D\ln INF_{it}$ = Change in the annual inflation rate (expressed as a percentage)

$D\ln INV_{it-1}$ = Lag in the gross fixed capital formation in agricultural processing industries

$D\ln TK_{it-1}$ = Lag of workers in agricultural processing industries

$D\ln INF_{it-1}$ = Lag in the inflation rate in agricultural processing industries

ECT = $\beta_7 (INV_{it-1} - TK_{it-1} + INF_{it-1})$

i = Cross-section units (12 regencies and cities in Southeast Sulawesi Province)

t = Time-series unit, 2011-2020

5. Selection of Analytical Model

Estimating the panel data regression model aims to predict the parameters of the regression model, i.e., the intercept or constant value (α) and the slope or regression coefficient (β). According to Widarjono (2007:251), there are three methods to estimate model parameters using panel data.

The Common Effect Model

The Common Effect model pools the time-series and cross-section data and uses the least-squares technique to estimate the coefficients. The regression equation is expressed in the following formula.

$$y_{it} = \alpha + x_{it}\beta + \varepsilon_{it}$$

$i = 1, 2, \dots, N$ and $t = 1, 2, \dots, T$. N is the number of cross-section units or individuals, and T is the period. This model will produce $N+T$ equations, i.e., T amount of cross-section equations and N amount of time-series equations.

The Fixed Effect Model

This model assumes that differences between individuals can be accommodated from differences in intercepts. A dummy variable technique estimates the fixed effect model with different intercepts between individuals, also known as the Least Squares Dummy Variable (LSDV) technique. The following is the regression equation.

$$y_{it} = \alpha_i + i\alpha_{it} + x'_{it}\beta + \varepsilon_{it}$$

$i = 1, 2, \dots, N$ and $t = 1, 2, \dots, T$. N is the number of cross-section units or individuals, and T is the period. This technique estimates the panel data using dummy variables to identify intercept differences.

The Random Effect Model

Estimating a data panel using this model will produce residuals that may be interconnected over time and between individuals. This model assumes differences in the intercept for each individual; the intercept is a random or stochastic variable.

The following is the regression equation.

$$y_{it} = \alpha_i + \beta'x_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (4.11)$$

In a random effect model, several assumptions must be met. Mathematically the assumptions are detailed in the following list.

$$E\{\varepsilon_{it}|X\} = E\{u_i|X\} = 0$$

$$E\{\varepsilon_{it}^2|X\} = \sigma_{\varepsilon^2} \text{ so } \varepsilon_{it} \sim N(0 \cdot \sigma_{\varepsilon^2})$$

$$E\{u_i^2|X\} = \sigma_{u^2} \text{ so } u_i \sim N(0 \cdot \sigma_{u^2})$$

$$E\{u_j \varepsilon_{it}|X\} = 0 \text{ for all } t, i \text{ dan } j$$

$$E\{u_i u_j|X\} = 0 \text{ if } i \neq j$$

$$E\{\varepsilon_{it} \varepsilon_{it'}|X\} = E(\varepsilon_{it}, \varepsilon_{it'}) = 0 \text{ if } (i \neq j) \text{ or } (t \neq s)$$

The above equation means that the error components are not correlated, and there is no autocorrelation between the cross-section and time-series. The suitable method for estimating the random effect model is Generalized Least Squares (GLS) with assumptions of homoscedastic and no cross-sectional correlation. GLS is an OLS with variable transformations that meet the standard assumptions of OLS. The OLS method cannot be used to obtain an efficient estimator.

Selection of Panel Data Regression Model

There are three tests to select the best panel data regression model between common, fixed, and random effect models.

a. The Chow test selects between the common and the fixed effect models. The following is the F test formula.

$$F_{\text{calculated}} = \frac{(RSS_1 - F)}{(RSS_2)}$$

RSS = Residual Sum of Squares; n = number of individuals; T = period; K = number of parameters in the fixed effect model. Each is a residual sum of squares, a non-dummy variable technique, and a fixed effect technique with dummy variables. The F statistic value will follow the distribution of the F statistic with a degree of freedom (df) of n-1 for the numerator and nT-k for the denominator. Suppose the value of probability F is less than the critical limit at a certain significance level. That case indicates that the fixed effect is better than the common effect technique. However, if the value of probability F exceeds the critical limit, the common effect is preferred over the fixed effect technique.

b. The Lagrange Multiplier (LM) Test

The Lagrange Multiplier (LM) test, which Bruesch-Pagan developed, can determine whether the random effect model is better than the common effect model. The following is the formula for the LM statistical value.

$$LM = \frac{nT}{2(T-1)} + \left[\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n [\sum_{t=1}^T \sigma_{it}]^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{t=1}^T \sigma_{it}^2} - 1 \right]$$

N = number of individuals; T = period; σ_{it} is the residual of the common effect method (OLS).

If the result of the LM statistic is greater than the chi-square critical value, then the best estimation for data panel regression is the random effect method. On the other hand, if the result of the LM statistic is less than the chi-square critical value, then the best estimation for data panel regression is the common effect method.

c. The Hausman Test

The Hausman test determines whether the fixed effect model is better than the random effect model. The Hausman value follows the chi-square distribution in the formula below based on the Wald criteria.

$$W = X^2[K] = [\hat{\beta} \hat{\beta}_{GLS}]' \sum^{-1} [\hat{\beta} - \hat{\beta}_{GLS}]$$

The Hausman test follows the chi-square statistical distribution with a degree of freedom as many as the number of independent variables. If the Hausman value is greater than the chi-square critical value, the fixed effect model is better for the panel data regression than the random effect model.

RESULTS

Stationarity Test

The stationarity test shows that the original data is not stationary at the level and became stationary at the first difference level. The stationarity test was carried out through a unit root test using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) approach before performing the Error Correction Model (ECM) test. The statistical estimation result of the unit root test at the first difference is shown in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1. First Difference Unit Root Test

Regency/ City	Variable	ADF Value	MacKinnon Critical Test			Prob	Remarks
			1%	5%	10%		
Kendari	Ln NP	-5.306	-5.835	-4.247**	-3.590*	0.0068	Stationary
	Ln INV	-5.976	-4.583***	-3.321**	-2.801*	0.0021	Stationary
	Ln TK	-2.523	-2.937	-2.006**	-1.598*	0.0202	Stationary
	Ln INF	-4.558	-2.886***	-1.996**	-1.599*	0.0006	Stationary
Konawe	Ln NP	-3.169	-2.937	-2.006	-1.598	0.0068	Stationary
	Ln INV	4.310	-4.804	-3.403**	-2.842*	0.0173	Stationary
	Ln TK	-2.473	-2.886	-1.995**	-1.599*	0.0210	Stationary
	Ln INF	-4.756	-4.583***	-3.321**	-2.801*	0.0203	Stationary
Konsel	Ln NP	-3.169	-2.937***	-2.006**	-1.598*	0.0068	Stationary
	Ln INV	-4.309	-4.804	-3.403**	-2.842*	0.0173	Stationary
	Ln TK	-2.473	-2.886	-1.996**	-1.599*	0.0210	Stationary
	Ln INF	-4.752	-4.583***	-3.321**	-2.801*	0.0203	Stationary
Konut	Ln NP	-4.322	-4.583	-3.321**	-2.801*	0.0138	Stationary
	Ln INV	-2.678	-2.886	-1.996**	-1.599*	0.0144	Stationary

	Ln TK	-7.106	-2.937***	-2.006**	-1.598*	0.0202	Stationary
	Ln INF	-4.558	-2.886***	-1.996**	-1.599*	0.0006	Stationary
Bau-Bau	Ln NP	-2.341	-2.937	-2.006**	-1.598*	0.0280	Stationary
	Ln INV	-6.392	-4.583***	-3.321**	-2.801*	0.0014	Stationary
	Ln TK	-2.624	-2.937	-2.006**	-1.598*	0.0169	Stationary
	Ln INF	-4.458	-4.583	-3.321**	-2.801*	0.0146	Stationary
Buton	Ln NP	-5.793	-2.886***	-1.996**	-1.599*	0.0001	Stationary
	Ln INV	-3.851	-4.804	-3.403**	-2.842*	0.0293	Stationary
	Ln TK	-4.381	-4.421	-3.260**	-2.771*	1.0000	Stationary
	Ln INF	-4.457	-4.804	-3.403**	-2.842*	0.0146	Stationary
Butur	Ln NP	-4.062	-6.292	-4.450	--3.701*	0.9963	Stationary
	Ln INV	-4.334	-4.804	-3.403**	-2.842*	0.0168	Stationary
	Ln TK	-4.793	-4.583***	-3.321**	-2.801*	0.0078	Stationary
	Ln INF	-4.457	-4.804	-3.403**	-2.842*	0.0146	Stationary
Kolaka	Ln NP	-4.827	-4.804	-3.403**	-2.842*	0.0097	Stationary
	Ln INV	-4.555	-4.804	-3.403**	-2.842*	0.0131	Stationary
	Ln TK	-3.851	-4.583	-3.321**	-2.801*	0.0250	Stationary
	Ln INF	-4.751	-4.583	-3.321**	-2.801*	0.0082	Stationary
Kolut	Ln NP	-5.107	-4.582***	-3.321**	-2.801*	0.0054	Stationary
	Ln INV	-8.162	-2.886***	-1.996**	-1.599*	0.0000	Stationary
	Ln TK	-9.979	-2.886***	-1.996**	-1.599*	0.0001	Stationary
	Ln INF	-4.752	-4.582***	-3.321**	-2.801*	0.0082	Stationary
Muna	Ln NP	-6.860	-4.803***	-3.403**	-2.842*	0.0009	Stationary
	Ln INV	-7.485	-4.803***	-3.403**	-2.842*	0.0000	Stationary
	Ln TK	-7.342	-4.583***	-3.321**	-2.801*	0.0005	Stationary
	Ln INF	-4.752	-4.582***	-3.321**	-2.801*	0.0082	Stationary
Bombana	Ln NP	-6.860	-4.804***	-3.403**	-2.842*	0.0009	Stationary
	Ln INV	7.485	-4.803***	-3.403**	-2.842*	0.0000	Stationary
	Ln TK	-7.341	-4.583***	-3.321**	-2.801*	0.0005	Stationary
	Ln INF	-4.752	-4.583***	-3.321**	-2.801*	0.0082	Stationary
Wakatobi	Ln NP	-4.253	-2.886***	-1.996**	-1.599*	0.0010	Stationary
	Ln INV	-3.031	-2.937***	-2.006**	-1.598*	0.0086	Stationary
	Ln TK	-7.341	-4.582***	-3.321**	-2.801*	0.0005	Stationary
	Ln INF	-4.457	-4.804	-3.403**	-2.842*	0.0146	Stationary

Remarks: ***Stationary at 1% Mackinnon critical test **Stationary at 5% Mackinnon critical test
* Stationary at 10% Mackinnon critical test

The estimation result of the unit root test at the first difference, as shown in Table 4.1, demonstrates that all variables have subsequently performed a cointegration test using a long-term regression equation. The first step in estimating the long-term equation through the cointegration test is to determine the correct panel regression model.

The selection of panel data regression is the stage to determine the best estimation method between common effect, fixed effect, and random effect.

a. Chow Test (Selecting between the Common Effect or Fixed Effect Models)

Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	7.051857	(11,105)	0.0000
Cross-section Chi-square	66.381074	11	0.0000

Table 4.1 shows that p-value from the cross-section chi-square is $0,000 < \alpha=0,05$. Therefore, H0 is rejected, which means that the fixed effect model is better than the common effect model.

b. Hausman Test(Selecting between the Fixed Effect and the Random Effect Models)

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
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Result of the Error Correction Model (ECM) Estimation

Based on Table 4.4, the estimation result of the ECM regression or short-term model shows that the ECT variable (residual) is significant with a probability of 0.0033, which is less than the 5% confidence level. Therefore, the ECM approach is valid and can be used to analyse the factors that affect the production value.

Table 4.4. ECM Estimation Result

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	90267.65	17896.16	5.043967	0.0000
INV?	0.291031	0.110976	2.622463	0.0105
TK?	0.490313	0.135055	3.630461	0.0005
INF?	0.174088	0.090542	1.922744	0.0583
RESID?(-1)	-0.470180	0.113086	-4.157742	0.0001
Fixed Effects (Cross)				
_KENDARI--C	6582.752			
_KONAWA--C	1887.661			
_KONSEL--C	5329.818			
_KOLUT--C	14098.58			
_BAU--C	-841.4567			
_BUTON--C	-8481.721			
_BUTUR--C	-3660.190			
_MUNA--C	2336.466			
_BOMBANA--C	-5041.411			
_WAKATOBI--C	-12210.50			
R-squared	0.778416	Mean dependent var		180775.7
Adjusted R-squared	0.740513	S.D. dependent var		13721.37
F-statistic	20.53727	Durbin-Watson stat		2.178010
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Table 4.2 and 4.3 presents the result of the ECM estimation using the fixed effect model. They show individual differences in the long and short term. The difference is observed in the data of Kendari and Bau-Bau, two cities in Southeast Sulawesi. Kendari has a C value of 5446356, while Bau-bau's value is -1704,335. Meanwhile, in the short term, Kendari has a C value of 6582,752, while Bau-bau has a value of -841,481,721. The two cities are both administrative towns, but there are differences in the characteristics of agricultural processing industries in their respective regions.

The result of the ECM estimation using the fixed effect model shows that the variables used in this study significantly affect the production value of agricultural processing industries, both in the short and long term. The independent variables included in the model are relatively good, with an adjust R2 value of 0.74 or 74%, because the diversity of dependent variables affected by independent variables outside the model is only about 26%. The estimation shows that investment, labour, and inflation simultaneously affect agricultural processing industries in Southeast Sulawesi, both in the long and short term, by obtaining a significance value of 0.000000 F, which is smaller than alpha 0.05 ($0.00 < 0.05$).

Furthermore, the ECM estimation using the fixed effect model demonstrates that investment had a significant positive effect in the long and short term between 2011-2020. The positive investment coefficient value is 0.296 in the long term, while the probability F statistic value is 0.0014, smaller than the significance level value. 0.05. Therefore, an increase in investment by 1 million IDR will increase the production value of agricultural processing industries by 0.29 million IDR in the long term. Meanwhile, in the short term, the positive investment coefficient is 0.285724, and the probability F statistic is 0.000000, which is less than alpha 0.05 ($0.00 < 0.05$). Thus, an increase in investment by 1 million IDR will increase the production value of agricultural processing industries by 0.285 million IDR in the short term. The result means that an increase in investment will increase the production value of agricultural processing industries in Southeast Sulawesi, and changes in investment will cause fluctuations in the production value.

Furthermore, the workforce had a significant positive effect, both long and short term. In the long term, the positive labour coefficient is 0.3045, and the probability F statistic is 0.0098, lower than the 0.05 significance value. Thus, an increase in the workforce by 1 million IDR will increase the production value of agricultural processing industries by 0.3045 million IDR in the long term. Meanwhile, in the short term, the positive investment coefficient is 0.378927, and the probability F statistic is 0.0032, which is smaller than alpha 0.05

(0.0032 < 0.05). Thus, an increase in the workforce of 1 million IDR will increase the production value of agricultural processing industries by 0.379 million IDR in the short term. It can be concluded that an increase in the workforce will increase the production value of processing industries in Southeast Sulawesi. Labour had a significant role in managing capital to produce quality products.

Meanwhile, inflation showed have no significant effect on the production value of agricultural products, both in the long and short term. The long term shows a probability F statistic of 0.099, greater than 0.05, and a coefficient value of 0.133. Meanwhile, in the short term, the positive inflation coefficient is 0.181307, and the probability F statistic is 0.0583, which is greater than alpha 0.05 (0.0583 < 0.05). The people's purchasing power will decrease due to price increases, but in the long term, the consumption behaviour will adjust to market prices, primarily in fulfilling basic needs. This finding agrees with studies by Fakhri (2011), Majumder (2016), and Malik & Chowdhury (2001).

The agricultural processing industries in Southeast Sulawesi is dominated by small and medium-sized industries that process food ingredients with relatively small and fluctuating investment values, dominated by domestic investment. This condition had an impact on low employment. The low investment is influenced by the unavailability of industrial estates that makes it easier for investors to obtain industrial land with complete facilities, as well as market information in carrying out industrial development. In addition, unsustainable raw materials and local product marketing affected the production process. This condition agrees with the study by Ernawati et al. (2020) that fishery processing industries in the South Konawe Regency were experiencing problems with the inconsistent availability of raw materials and local marketing. Also, Sufa (2021) discovered that seaweed industries in the form of ATC CHIPS in Southeast Sulawesi were experiencing problems procuring raw seaweed materials from farmers. The annual seaweed production was 93,660 kg, while the need was 1,080,000 kg annually. Nuryadi et al. (2017) stated that the seaweed farmer issue was due to seaweed management which only focused on the production and did not consider the agribusiness aspect. It is one of the reasons why agribusiness has not developed in Southeast Sulawesi.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

1. Investment, labour, and inflation can explain as much as 74% of the production value of agricultural processing industries. Other variables outside this study influence the remaining 26%.
2. Investment, labour, and inflation simultaneously affected the production value of agricultural processing industries in Southeast Sulawesi.
3. Investment and labour had positive and significantly effect on the production value of agricultural processing industries, both in the short and long term. Meanwhile, inflation have no significant effect in the short and long term.
4. The development of agricultural production value in Southeast Sulawesi was dominated by small and medium enterprises, i.e., local food industries with small and fluctuating investments, which resulted in low employment. The local businesses also face unsustainable raw material issues, leading to suboptimal production processes.
5. To increase the agricultural processing industry's contribution to the GRDP (Gross Regional Domestic Product) of the processing industry sector, the government must take several actions. The agricultural productivity needs to be increased to maintain the sustainability of industrial raw materials, and the development of industrial estates needs to be accelerated to maintain the investment climate. In addition, it is also necessary to provide community entrepreneurship education and training, especially for farmers, in processing materials into competitive industrial products to expand markets, provide added value, and create jobs.

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